

Soil biological quality index (QBS) determination using machine learning

Version 1

Description

Using microscopy images of soil arthropods to determine QBS-ar by building machine learning models.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Soil biological quality index (QBS) determination using machine learning (Izp-2024/1-0643)

Researchers

Antra Boca (0000-0002-5040-7998), Ugis Kagainis (0000-0002-9921-2331), Roberts Kadikis (0000-0001-6845-4381)

Organizations

University of Latvia, Institute of Electronics and Computer Science

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Soil biological quality index (QBS) determination using machine learning

Description:

Using microscopy images of soil arthropods to determine QBS-ar by building machine learning models.

Researchers:

Antra Boca (0000-0002-5040-7998)

Ugis Kagainis (0000-0002-9921-2331)

Roberts Kadiķis (0000-0001-6845-4381)

Organizations:

University of Latvia

Institute of Electronics and Computer Science

Contact: Boča Antra (antra.boca@lu.lv), Kagainis Uģis (ugis.kagainis@lu.lv), Kadiķis Roberts (roberts.kadikis@edi.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: Soil biological quality index (QBS) determination using machine learning (Izp-2024/1-0643)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-04-04

4. Templates

Descriptions

Soil biological quality index (QBS) determination using machine learning

The main objective of this project is to develop machine learning models to determine the soil biological quality index (QBS-ar) by analyzing images of the soil microarthropod community extracted from soil samples. The models and the operating procedure for the method will be designed with an intended use in large-scale studies, e.g., soil monitoring programs.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Images of soil microarthropod community for building a machine learning model for the determination of the QBS-ar index.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Programme source code
- Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV
- PNG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, but we could not find such data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

other researchers interested in soil fauna and machine model building for small object detection

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

ABCD (Access to Biological Collection Data)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

QBS-ar, soil arthropods, small object detection

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

YOLO

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

GitHub

DataverseLV

<https://dataverse.lv/>

University repository with quality check from data stewards

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Python

any image editor

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

We'll use widespread image formats provided above.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-09

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2048-01-09

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Antra Boca (0000-0002-5040-7998)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

